

Software Design and the PATH Preprocessor

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Abstract

PATH is a nonsmooth Newton method for solving nonlinear complementarity problems, which have many applications in economics and engineering. This general-purpose code is capable of solving problem instances generated by non-expert users within algebraic modeling languages, such as AMPL and GAMS. To improve reliability on difficult problems, many algorithmic enhancements have been incorporated into the code. One key enhancement is the preprocessor that automatically applies a series of reductions to a given problem to produce a more compact problem that is usually easier to solve. The preprocessor implementation, however, is complex and accounts for roughly 25% of the entire PATH code. The software design process for the PATH preprocessor is described in this report, which starts from a mathematical analysis that identifies the reductions that can be applied to generic problems, the reductions then dictate the requirements for data structures and algorithms, and an extensible implementation follows. A discussion of the limitations in the reductions that can be easily implemented and the difficulty of designing a comprehensive testing plan due to the software design choices is provided. While the implementation of the PATH preprocessor satisfies the requirements and is functional, greater emphasis on extensibility, testability, and maintainability during the software design might have helped to lessen these limitations.

Introduction. PATH [4, 8, 9] implements a nonsmooth Newton method for general nonlinear complementarity problems. The nonlinear complementarity problem is to find a vector $x \in \Re^n$ such that

$$0 \leq x \perp f(x) \geq 0,$$

where $f : \Re^n \rightarrow \Re^n$ is a continuously differentiable function and $x \perp f(x) \Leftrightarrow x^T f(x) = 0$, the complementarity condition. These problems arise in many economic and engineering applications [12] and can be used to model competition via Nash and Cournot games, economic equilibria, and free-boundary problems, such as physical models that include phase changes. These problems are generally difficult to solve due to the combinatorial nature of the complementarity condition, while certain problem classes, such as when f is a strongly monotone function, can be solved in polynomial time.

The PATH algorithm solves a linear complementarity problem at each iteration

$$0 \leq x \perp \nabla f(x^k)(x - x^k) + f(x^k) \geq 0,$$

where x^k is the current iterate. The method is stabilized using a one-dimensional search along the direction to ensure global convergence to stationary points for a merit function [6]. This linear complementarity problem is solved with a version of Lemke's method [14, 15], which constructs a piecewise linear path from an initial starting point to a solution. The implementation contains many algorithmic enhancements, such as the use of a crashing method to obtain an initial starting point and basis [5] and proximal point regularization to improve the conditioning of the systems [1], leading to a divergence between the implementation and the algorithm described in the literature.

One enhancement in particular is the preprocessor [10] that takes as input a nonlinear complementarity problem and some extra information, applies a sequence of reductions that usually make the problem easier to solve, and outputs the resulting more compact representation of the problem. This preprocessor and the additional diagnostics it supports is one of the key elements to the success of PATH on difficult problems.

The price paid for the preprocessor, however, is code complexity, where over 25% of the entire PATH source code is currently devoted to the preprocessor.

The basic design of the preprocessor is based on a mathematical analysis to identify possible reductions. The reduction logic is then implemented in the software to produce a set of rules that are applied sequentially, starting from simple rules and proceeding to complex rules. The reductions dictate the requirements for the data structures and algorithms used in the implementation. The software design also needs to be extensible so that when new reductions are discovered from the mathematical analysis, they can be easily integrated. The early identification of the types of reductions to implement and the chosen data structures, however, limited the reductions that could be easily implemented without redesigning the preprocessor. Testing the implementation introduces another challenge, as it can be difficult to construct problems that test each individual rule due to the complex branching required.

In the remainder of this report, the software design process for the PATH preprocessor is described, which starts from a mathematical analysis that identifies the reductions that can be applied to generic problems, the reductions then dictate the requirements for the data structures and algorithms, and an extensible implementation follows. A discussion of the limitations in the reductions that can be easily implemented and the difficulty of designing a comprehensive testing plan due to the software design choices is provided before concluding.

Mathematical Analysis. The concept of a preprocessor for nonlinear complementarity problems begins with a mathematical analysis to identify a set of reductions that can be made, assuming we know which elements of the Jacobian matrix are linear and nonlinear. This extra information is either provided by the modeling language or the user.

One key mathematical analysis tool is the equivalence between a nonlinear complementarity problem with a skew symmetric structure

$$\begin{array}{rcl} 0 \leq x & \perp & f(x) - A^T \lambda \geq 0 \\ 0 \leq \lambda & \perp & Ax \geq b \end{array}$$

and a polyhedral variational inequality where the polyhedron is $\{x \mid x \geq 0, Ax \geq b\}$ [16]. Preprocessing with this skew symmetric structure consists of changing the algebraic representation of the geometric set through simple transformations that reduce the number of algebraic constraints while preserving the shape of the polytope. These transformations can be simply replacing a general constraint $a_i x_i \geq b_i$ by the simpler bound $x_i \geq \max\{0, b_i/a_i\}$ when $a_i > 0$, to more complicated rules, such as when we can infer that an inequality constraint can never be binding at a solution and therefore can be removed from the general constraints as redundant. When we are provided with a general nonlinear complementarity problems, the skew symmetric structure is not provided by the user and must be identified by the implementation.

Beyond skew symmetric transformations, general transformations based on the diagonal blocks can be performed. Prediagonal and postdiagonal blocks are such that the problem has the structure

$$\begin{array}{rcl} 0 \leq x & \perp & Bx \geq c \\ 0 \leq y & \perp & g(x, y) \geq 0 \\ 0 \leq z & \perp & h(x, y) + Cz \geq 0. \end{array}$$

The prediagonal block can be eliminated when the subproblem $0 \leq x \perp Bx \geq c$ has a unique solution, while the postdiagonal block can be eliminated when there exists a solution to the subproblem $0 \leq z \perp h(x, y) + Cz \geq 0$ for any vector in the closure of the range of h given the available bounds on x and y . The simplest existence result is when C is a positive definite matrix [3]. As with the skew symmetric rules, block structure is not provided by the user and must be identified by the implementation.

These rules are applied sequentially starting from the simple rules to the more complicated rules and we iterate until either a maximum number of iterations is exceeded or no further reductions or modifications are made. As we iterate and variables and constraints are fixed and removed, new skew symmetric and block structures may be revealed that can lead to more reductions. Hence, the structural analysis needs to be repeated. Moreover, the sequence of transformations needs to be recorded so that once the transformed problem is solved, the transformations can be undone in the reverse order via a postprocessor to compute the solution to the original problem. For example, in the postprocessor for a post diagonal block, we need to actually compute a solution to the subproblem $0 \leq z \perp h(x^*, y^*) + Cz \geq 0$, where x^* and y^* is the solution returned by the main PATH algorithm.

Data Structures and Algorithms. Having performed the analysis, we can identify the information, data structures, and algorithms required for the implementation. In order to apply the preprocessor, we need additional information about the problem in order to identify the nonlinear and linear elements of the problem. Without this additional information, the problem must be assumed to be nonlinear and no transformations can be performed. Therefore, we augment the problem interface to include a call back function that fills in a structure to identify the linear parts of the Jacobian matrix. This information is supplied automatically when the user specifies their problems in an algebraic modeling language, such as GAMS [2] or AMPL [13], and can be supplied by the user in other cases.

Once we have the necessary information, a key time consuming element of the preprocessor could be matching the structure of the problem to the required structure for the application of a particular rule. The matching needs to be efficient so that the cost of preprocessing does not dominate the computational savings from solving the transformed problem versus the original problem. To reduce the matching cost, we need easy access the rows and columns of the Jacobian matrix. Initially the Jacobian matrix is stored in a compressed sparse column format that we augment so that we can also walk through the matrix in a compressed sparse row format. We then maintain an invariant on the transformed problem that the row and column nonzero counts are updated as variables and constraints are fixed and eliminated, rather than recomputed. Based on the nonzero counts, we add rows and columns to a queue from which we can apply simple, fast reductions for rows or columns with up to three nonzeros. During the preprocessing process, we remove the first element from the queue and apply the appropriate rule. If a reduction is made, we update the nonzero counts of only the affected rows and columns and add those whose nonzero counts are small enough to the queue for processing. Once the queue is empty, we proceed to more complicated rules.

Application of the skew symmetry rules requires that we first find the skew symmetric structure within a general problem. This identification is performed in two phases. This first phase checks each row against the corresponding column to see if the nonzero patterns are the same and then checks if they are numerically skew symmetric. When such a skew symmetric row is identified, we mark it as skew symmetric and apply the available rules for a single skew symmetric row.

Having the list of the single skew symmetric rows and columns, the second phase identifies skew symmetric blocks by applying a greedy algorithm to build up blocks of rows and columns that are skew symmetric. This algorithm starts from one skew symmetric row and adds the next compatible row by walking through the compressed sparse matrix representations. In this way we can build maximal skew symmetric blocks. After one block is identified, we start the process with any remaining single skew symmetric row and repeat until there are no more possible blocks. Once the skew symmetric blocks are identified, we can proceed to apply the specialized block skew symmetric rules. Additional diagnostics from the construction of the skew symmetric blocks can be provided to the user, such as when the skew symmetry is not present due to a sign reversal or a scaling factor.

The rules for prediagonal and postdiagonal blocks are fundamentally tied to the analysis of linear complementarity problems. Similar to the skew symmetry detection, we identify blocks based on the nonzero pattern by applying a greedy algorithm that starts from a single constraint and adds constraints until either a block is identified or block becomes too big and is no longer viable for the prediagonal and postdiagonal block rules. When the identified B or C matrix is positive definite, for example, the solution to the subproblem is unique and the prediagonal or postdiagonal block can be removed from the complementarity problem. The available theory is incomplete for prediagonal blocks and the approach we take is to compute all solutions by enumeration of the possible complementarities for up to 2×2 systems and check positive definiteness for larger problems. The solution to a 2×2 complementarity problem can be the union of points, line segments, and subsets of planes. We produce the minimal representation of the solution and report it in a structure capable of representing the union. Extending this analysis to larger problem sizes is possible, but can be time consuming due to the enumeration and requires extending the union for the solution to include higher dimensional subsets. At times the solution to the prediagonal block may only be partially unique, but can be eliminated if the nonunique solution variables are not used in the remainder of the problem.

As the rules are successfully applied, the necessary information for postprocessing is captured in a structure and pushed to a stack. When the postprocessor is applied, a structures is successively popped from the stack and the relevant postprocessing rule is applied. This process is repeated until the stack is empty and we have produced a solution to the original nonlinear complementarity problem supplied by the user.

Extensible Implementation. The software design also needs to be extensible so that when new rules are discovered from the mathematics, they can be integrated into the preprocessor. Moreover, there is a desire to be able to identify and remove redundant rules. Our implementation separates the rules by types and encapsulates their implementation in separate files that contains a driver within that file to apply them. To add or remove a rule requires implementing the rule and adding it to the corresponding driver. Adding a new rule type requires creating a new file and driver and then calling the driver in the looping code that performs the matching.

Limitations. More complicated preprocessing rules involve changes to the model and/or structure of the Jacobian matrix. When the skew symmetry is not identified due to a sign reversal or a scaling factor, we could automatically modify the function and Jacobian evaluations to fix the issues and possibly change the matching of the variables in the complementarity conditions. We currently only report these issues to the user, as they might be addressable by more careful modeling. Even more complicated rules involve block elimination using the Schur complement that can increase or decrease the number of nonzeros in the resulting problem and sparsification or common subexpression elimination that can add rows and columns to the problem, while the resulting Jacobian matrix will be sparser than the original. Moreover, when a variable is fixed and removed we can in principle walk through the function and Jacobian evaluations routines to determine if some of the nonlinear entries become linear. Such rules that involve structural modifications have not been incorporated into the current software design, limiting what can be done by the preprocessor. Adding these capabilities would involve substantial changes to the evaluation of the function and Jacobian and possibly keeping extra copies of this information, increasing the complexity of the preprocessor implementation.

Testing the preprocessor introduces another challenge in the software design, as it can be difficult to construct problems that test each of the individual rules. We have constructed test problems throughout the years and maintain a large test set of real problems that we use for this purpose, but cannot guarantee that it exercises all possible branches in the code. We run this test set prior to any release of the software. We also provide access to copious diagnostics from the preprocessor to output the sequence rules that were applied for debugging purposes. The rules themselves are also documented in the code with their pre and post conditions. Manually calling the individual rules with appropriate inputs, rather than providing test problems, would be required for proper testing. The file-based implementation could support such manual tests, but would require additional thought on how best to implement this scheme and to modify the build system to run these tests and collect and present the results.

Conclusion. The complex software design challenges are partially overcome in the design of the PATH preprocessor. By taking a systematic approach from the mathematical analysis to the design of the data structures and algorithms, we can provide a very complex piece of code that makes general problems supplied by the user easier to solve, while limiting the complexity that we need to consider in each individual set of rules. The design has gone through several iterations to ensure that it is efficient and extensible. However, a new software design would be required to incorporate rules based on modifying the structure of the problem. This complexity has not yet been considered, as the current preprocessor is already very complex. Moreover, testing is difficult due to all the branches, so getting coverage is a challenge without manual testing of rules. With an improved software design that considers structural modifications and testing needs, we would hope to limit the complexity of the implementation and make the preprocessing software even more extensible and useful. While the current implementation of the PATH preprocessor satisfies the requirements and is functional, greater emphasis on extensibility, testability, and maintainability during the software design might have helped to lessen these limitations.

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